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Speech Therapists and Parents Working Together to Support Pre-schoolchildren with Speech Pathologies

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Abstract

Problem of research: The modern parent is increasingly an active participant in the educational, correctional process, he is engaged in various discussions with speech therapists working with their child about the choice and application of productive correction methods. The parent is no longer excluded from the process of correction, but, on the contrary, he is in charge of overcoming disorders in children. Thus, the interaction of speech therapists and parents in the system of correctional and speech therapeutical assistance to children with different speech impairments of preschool age is relevant, since it requires revising and adjusting the methods of cooperation.

Purpose: to show the features of the interaction of speech therapists and parents in the system of correctional and speech therapeutical help to children with various speech disorders of preschool age in the conditions of the modern correctional school.

Methods: the work under study contains all the structural parts of a scientific experiment that reflects the qualitative assessment of the results obtained, which allows scrutinizing the various characteristics of the criteria studied. The present research also looks at the qualitative characteristics of organizational, methodological and other aspects of effective interaction between speech specialists and parents in the system of correctional and speech therapeutical assistance to children with various speech disorders of preschool age in educational establishments.

Results: the article describes the identified difficulties in the interaction of speech therapists and parents in the system of correctional speech therapy for children. The current study revealed some difficulties in raising a child with various speech disorders in the family, as well as the preferred forms of communication.

Conclusions and recommendations: organizational, methodological and other aspects of effective interaction of speech therapists and parents in the system of correction and speech therapy for children with various speech disorders of preschool age in an educational organization are revealed.

Keywords: interaction, speech therapists and parents, children with speech disorders, preschoolers, correctional and speech therapy assistance, up-to-date.

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Introduction

Recently, the interest of teachers and heads of preschool organizations to work with the family has noticeably increased. This is due to different aspects, on the one hand, the active interest of parents in the process of correcting disorders in their own children, on the other hand, estrangement from action during the correctional process, which takes a long period, from a few months to several years. Recent trends in the education system lead to the need for change not only in the system of training and correction itself, but also approaches to the interaction of teachers and parents. This is confirmed by the numerous changes in society, the complex socio-economic and environmental conditions of modern times, which shows the need to find and develop new approaches to the implementation of educational tasks in an educational establishment. According to the Concept of Modernization of Russian Education, the family should become an active subject of educational policy. The achievement of the strategic goals of modernization of education is possible only in the process of constant interaction of the educational system with various representatives, including the family as a social unit.

Back in 2012 the law “On Education in the Russian Federation” was adopted. Despite some revision in 2016–2017, it clearly defines “general principles and provisions governing these relations in the education system”. Strengthening the educational and educational functions of preschool institutions, as well as changes occurring in the life of society, it is necessary to improve the forms and ways of interaction between the kindergarten and family, teachers and parents. The further development of the child depends on the joint work of parents and teachers. And the level of pedagogical culture of parents, and, consequently, the level of family upbringing of children, depends on the quality of work of a pre-school institution. In order for professionals working with children with disabilities to be an authoritative source of information about reliable means and methods of corrective influence, we need special, productive, accessible and modern approaches to interacting with parents. As Krivokapic (2018) notes the influence of both parents and teachers in the early period of childhood development, when it comes to raising each child individually and “development of society as a whole”. Competent teacher is a key figure in the educational process. Only under this condition, parents with confidence will react to the recommendations of speech therapists, will be more willing to establish contact with them and participate in the correction process. Speech therapists and speech pathologists should constantly differentiate the ways of interaction, adjust the requirements for themselves, their pedagogical knowledge and skills, their attitude to children and parents. Today, the majority of kindergartens face a difficult task - to attract parents to pedagogical interaction with the child, while leaving the unproductive and outdated schemes of upbringing.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to show the features of the interaction of specialists and parents in the system of correctional and speech therapy assistance to children with various speech disorders of preschool age in the context of a modern correctional educational establishment.

To achieve this goal the following tasks have been put forward:

- to study the theoretical aspects of the problems of interaction between a speech therapist and the family;
- to consider the psychological and pedagogical foundations of the interaction between the family and speech therapist;

- to characterize the existing forms of interaction of a speech therapist with the families of children with general speech disorder and to conduct a research to identify the preferred and most effective forms of interaction between the speech therapist and parents;
- to identify their effectiveness in the course of the experiment;
- to systematize and characterize the forms of interaction of a speech therapist with the families of children with a general speech impairment.

Literature review

In recent years, the term “innovation” has been increasingly used in the pedagogical domain. This term means “advanced pedagogical experience”, “breakthrough that arises on the basis of a variety of initiatives promising for the development of education”. Currently, considerable practical experience has been gained in interacting with the families of pupils. However, not enough attention is paid to the work of preschool institutions with parents of children with speech disorders. Overcoming speech disorders is rather difficult and longitudinal process. To combat violations in preschool age provides an opportunity to master the school skills. It is impossible to make a child be engaged, he must be interested. And parents are the ones who can assist. Therefore, in overcoming the violations of the child, the leading role belongs to the adult: parents and speech therapists.

The idea of partnership of parents and teachers-speech pathologists in the upbringing and education of children with peculiar psychophysical development, including speech disorders, is reflected in a number of legal documents. Thus, from December 29, 2012, a new law “On Education in the Russian Federation” came out, in which for the first time pre-school education is defined as one of the levels of general education. This approach made it necessary to develop a federal state educational standard (GEF) for preschool education, which is currently being introduced into the system of preschool education. It is noted that one of the directions of state policy in the field of education is the socio-psychological support for families bringing up people with peculiar psychophysical impairment. Article 10 indicates that parents are part of the education system, parents can attend and participate in remedial classes, receive advice on training and education of people with peculiar psychophysical development (Law of the Russian Federation). In accordance with this, the position of institutions providing special assistance to children with speech disorders also changes. The main tasks in working with parents are: studying the family of a child with speech disorders; involvement of parents in active participation in the correctional-pedagogical process; increasing the level of psychological and pedagogical knowledge, skills and abilities of parents, enhancing their pedagogical self-education; organization of propaganda of positive experience of family education of children with speech disorders.

Parents can be socially isolated and limited in community support. Additional services do not always meet the needs of parents of children with learning disabilities, and working together between the teacher and the family is particularly problematic.

So, Morozova, Belogay, & Ott (2014) believes that “quality management of the educational process becomes possible only in the context of developing interaction between all participants in the educational process”. The authors described a new philosophy of interaction between teachers and parents, in which a detailed presentation is presented of the classification of children’s incomplete stay groups in accordance with the demands of the parents and for the best adaptation conditions. To accomplish these tasks, a speech therapist must have the following skills: build a relationship of trust with the child’s parents and family; carry out work to overcome the formation of distorted perceptions among parents about

possible quick positive results; build your family support on the safeguarding functions and abilities of the child, avoid fixing changes on existing violations and others.

The issue of interaction between teacher- speech pathologist and parents is given attention to in the works of Mastjukova & Moskovkina (2004), Tkacheva and others (1998, 1999). In the scientific literature we find evidence that the appearance in the family of a child with developmental disabilities is always associated with the emotional experiences of the parents. Tkacheva (1999) points out the need to study families with children with peculiar psychophysical development, and to develop a system of measures to provide them with psychological and educational assistance. The author notes that parents experience qualitative changes, which are manifested on the psychological, social levels. At a psychological level, parents are under stress, which is long-lasting, permanent, and has a drastic effect on parents' psyche.

In the study of Belousova et al. (2015) and others, the personality characteristics of preschoolers were described and they may cause difficulties in communication. In social terms, the family becomes selective in communication, there is a narrow circle of friends, and also the relationship between parents changes. At the somatic level, parents manifest asthenic and autonomic disorders.

Mishina (2001) highlighted the tendencies of disturbed behavior of mothers in organizing subject-game cooperation with their child: legislative cooperation; non-emotional-indulging cooperation; speech interaction; detachment interaction; formal communication.

The choice of forms and methods of studying the family is determined by the specific conditions of the institution, the personality characteristics of the teacher-speech pathologist, the peculiarities of family upbringing of children, the level of pedagogical culture of parents and other factors. Among the methods of studying the family, the most common are: the study of documentation, observation, questioning, interviewing, the study of products of activity, conversation and others.

The use of observation is effective to identify the relationship of the child with the parents in different conditions (during the morning meeting with the group, in the situation of the evening farewell of children and others). In the situation of the morning enrollment of children to the group, attention is paid to the following indicators: the mood of a child, parents (cheerful, indifferent, etc.); statements in the course of communication (approval, criticism, conversation, etc.); farewell (quick, long with persuasion, affectionate, with parting words, etc.); undressing procedure (himself, parents, together) and others. The behavior of parents in these moments reflects their educational installation.

The conversation allows the speech therapist to obtain anamnestic information, personal data about parents, information about the conditions of family education of children with speech disorders. When preparing and conducting the conversation, some common requirements should be taken into account:

1. Purpose, place and time of the upcoming conversation.
2. The list of questions, their sequence, wording.
3. Creating a relaxed atmosphere.
4. Possible reaction of parents to the questions of the conversation.
5. Showing tact and caution when assessing children, family members.
6. The results of the conversation should be compared with other methods.

Speaking with parents of children with speech disorders, there are special requirements that are described in the literature (Borodich, 2004).

Interviewing is a method of obtaining information through an oral survey. Two types of

interviews are commonly used: free, not regulated by the topic and form of the conversation, and standardized, which includes questions with suggested answers. The method of questioning is a written survey, which involves receiving answers from respondents to establish the facts. Tkacheva (1998) singled out the types of survey: contact (the researcher conducts himself); in absentia (questionnaires with instructions are sent to respondents).

For complex diagnostics of family and family education, tests, questionnaires, questionnaires, projective techniques are used, the use of which involves the cooperation of a speech therapist teacher with psychologists, social workers and other specialists. In this article, I would like to mention the basic methods of studying the family and family education:

1. Methods of diagnosing attitudes towards the child's illness (DOBR), developed by Kagan & Zhuravleva (1991).
2. PARI method was developed by Shefer & Bell (2001).
3. The method of diagnosis of parental attitudes (ORO), aimed at assessing the parental attitude as a system of diverse feelings towards the child. It was designed by Varga & Stolin (1988).
4. A questionnaire for parents "Analysis of family education (DIA)", aimed at identifying relationships in the education of children was coined by Eidemiller, Aleksandrova, & Yustitskis (2007).
5. Questionnaire for the study of the interaction of parents with children (CRF), used to diagnose parent-child relationships and interactions. It was proposed by Markovskaya (2005).
6. The family system test (FAST) by Göring and Vilera, designed to study family relationships and assess the hierarchy of relations between family members.
7. The projective technique "Family Drawing" (RS), evaluating intrafamily relations (described by Wulf, Korman, Zakharov). A variation is the kinetic pattern of the family (KRS) was proposed by Burns & Kaufman (2000).
8. René Gilles technique, designed to study the sphere of interpersonal relations of the child and his perception of intra-family relations.
9. Projective test "Family sociogram", aimed at identifying the position of a family member in the system of interpersonal relations.
10. The "Unfinished sentences" method used to identify the system of relations of the subject to the family. It was utilized by Sachs and Levy and others.

Thus, family research methods are aimed at identifying personal and basic characteristics, the study of rapport of a child and parents, indicating the self-concept of parents as educationalists.

The forms of work of a speech therapist teacher with parents are divided into three main groups:

- individual: conversations; consultations; workshops; attendance of classes; keeping notebooks for homework;
- group (collective): parent meetings; session of questions and answers; round table discussions; training sessions; joint holidays and entertainment; open door days; schools for parents; parent conferences; games, workshops; parents and children society, etc;
- visual information: exhibitions of children's work; photo exhibitions; advertising of books, articles from newspapers, magazines; information bank; stands; folder-shifting; libraries; thematic exhibitions; sanitary bulletin; information baskets (box, boxes) = parent mail; reminders; advertising booklets, flyers, posters, videos; helpline, moneybox tips and others.

When choosing a form of work, a speech therapist should implement an individual approach to parents and children. At the initial stages of interaction, individual forms of work are used: demonstration

of the mother's methods of working with the child, note-taking of individual lessons, homework, reading mothers of special literature recommended by the speech therapist. In drawing up individual correctional and developmental training programs for a child with speech disorder, the structure of his speech defect, general health, age, and personality characteristics are taken into account.

The stages of individual counseling of parents in special institutions are presented in the studies of Volkovskaya, Strebelova, Filipovich and others. The first stage (diagnostic) establishes a trusting relationship with parents (using conversation, interview, experimentally psychological techniques, if necessary).

The second stage is carried out on the basis of the examination of the child. At this stage, the speech therapist informs the parents about the state of the child's speech, overall mental development, explains the measures of assistance taking into account the structure of the defect, and plans subsequent meetings to discuss the dynamics of the child's advancement under the influence of correction.

At the third stage of counseling, which is correlated with correctional work, the following tasks are performed: increasing the level of pedagogical competence of parents through expanding the range of knowledge in the field of speech therapy; inclusion of parents in the system of correctional assistance. The most effective forms of interaction between a speech therapist and parents are: joint discussions with parents on the progress and results of correctional work; making recommendations to overcome negative trends in the development of the child; conducting individual workshops on training parents (articulation, breathing, voice types of gymnastics, etc.).

The fourth stage (final) of counseling is advisory. The positive result of this stage will be a change in the attitude of the parents towards the child towards the adoption of its features.

One of the most effective forms of work with parents is counseling, the topics of which are varied: "How to prepare a child with speech disorders for school?", "Teaching children to read speech disorders", "Preventing voice disorders in children", "Preventing stuttering children".

The improvement of psychological and pedagogical knowledge aimed at overcoming speech disorders in children is carried out in the process of individual and group training for parents. In the work of Tkacheva (1999), methods of psychological assistance are presented to families raising children with peculiar psychophysical development. The content of the classes offered by the author with his parents is aimed at harmonizing family relationships; assistance in an adequate assessment of the physical and psychological capabilities of the child; the development of communicative behaviors that promote self-actualization (1998); teaching the mother special remedial, methodological and educational techniques necessary to conduct classes with the child at home.

The choice of group forms of interaction between a speech therapist and parents is determined by the degree of their readiness to cooperate. Thus, the group form of work with parents with low motivation can be recommended from the second half of the school year. One of the common group forms of working with parents are parent meetings. For example, the first parent meeting in a preschool institution is held in late September. At this meeting, the speech therapist covers the following issues: the need for special training for children with speech disorders, analyzes the results of speech therapy of children (indicating common difficulties, and during individual interviews informs parents about the results of the examination of their child); reports on the organization and content of the work during the year; informs on the adoption of additional measures in the presence of violations related to the main defect (eye and hearing impairment).

It is useful to let the parents listen to the recordings of speech statements of children received

during the initial examination. The second parent meeting is held following the results of the first half of the year - in January. It discusses the dynamics of the movement of children, the objectives and content of education in the second half of the year. According to the results of the school year (in May), the third parent meeting is organized, where the data of the re-examination of children are presented, and recommendations are given for their further education and upbringing.

Workshops for parents are interconnected with group consultations and contribute to the formation of the necessary practical skills among parents. Workshop topics include:

- the use of articulation gymnastics in correctional work on the formation of the correct pronunciation;
- the formation of graphic skills in children in order to prepare hands for writing;
- teaching children coherent speech using graphical schemes;
- development of finger motor skills;
- teaching children to compare subjects;
- development of spatial and temporal representations in children during the period of preparation for school and others.

The homework notebook contains material on which parents work their pronunciation (syllables, words, chatter, poems, riddles, and stories). The notebook contains exercises that develop articulatory motor skills, speech breathing, voice, etc. At first, the tasks offered at home are dealt with in detail with children and parents. It is important to focus the attention of parents on the implementation of these tasks and encouraging the child's desire to do them.

Teacher-speech therapist makes parents stand for other specialists, updating the material at least once a month. At the stand can be placed material on the formation of children's sound pronunciation, improvement of grammatical means of speech, development of cognitive processes, advice to parents on preventing and overcoming speech disorders, games and exercises, current information for parents and other.

To coordinate the work of all services of the institution, an effective form of working with parents is the "information basket". For example, under the conditions of the Center for Correctional and Developmental Education and Rehabilitation, it may include: the activities of the institution, the date, the content of the request, the proposals, to whom it is addressed, information on the measures taken, diagnostic, correctional and developmental, early comprehensive care, socio-psychological, methodical section.

Modern methods of interaction include trainings, workshops, videos, which are placed in the space provided for parents, also project activities are organized in the pre-school, as described in the work of Mikhailova, Ilyushina, & Manayeva (2018), also described in the main educational program of preschool education for 2015–2020.

Thus, promising forms of work of a speech therapist teacher with parents are:

- the creation of a reference and information database on the upbringing and education of children with speech disorders;
- ensuring continuity in work with parents between institutions providing speech therapy assistance;
- the involvement of the media in the problems of prevention of overcoming speech disorders in children;
- strengthening the visual-informational group of forms of work with parents.

Thus, the modern concept of pre-school education initiated the reform of pre-school education, in which it is indicated that the family and pre-school educational institutions, having their own special functions, cannot replace each other. The Law of the Russian Federation "On Education" (2012) states that one of the main tasks facing the kindergarten is "interaction with the family to ensure family upbringing of children with speech disorders.

The importance of this problem is confirmed by the research of such scientists as Winnicott et al. (1993), Bronfenbrenner (1992), Bowlby (2003), Ainsworth (1978), who revealed that the basis of social adaptation a child in the first year of life has feelings of affection for close adults. At the same time, the types of attachment of a child to parents (adults) identified by the authors are considered as conditions for its social adaptation. They consider the family as the closest social environment of the child, satisfying the child's need for acceptance, recognition, protection, emotional support, respect. The family, according to scientists, can be a factor affecting the success of the social adaptation of a preschooler child, as well as one of the causes of social maladjustment of the individual. At the same time, the nature of parent-child relationships is highlighted as the main condition for social adaptation of a preschooler child (Winnicott et al., 1993; Bowlby, 2003).

Methodology

This work contains all the structural parts of a scientific experiment that reflects not only the qualitative assessment of the results obtained, which allows to leverage the various characteristics of the criteria studied, but also the qualitative characteristics of the organizational, methodological and other aspects of the effective interaction of specialists and parents in the system of correctional speech therapy for children with various speech disorders of preschool age in an educational organization.

The following methods were used: the study of theoretical and scientific-methodological literature on the research topic; learning pedagogical experience; diagnostic methods, observation, analysis and synthesis of the obtained data.

Our study included several stages.

At the first stage, the study and analysis of scientific and pedagogical work on the research problem was carried out. The most significant ways of interaction of teachers with a child's family with impaired development were described.

At the second stage, a model of teacher interaction with parents in the ONR correction system for older preschoolers was developed and tested.

At the third stage, a final experiment was conducted, the purpose of which was to identify the dynamics of speech development and to identify the effectiveness of the forms of interaction used.

The study was conducted in the 7th senior group of a kindergarten № 213 in Rostov-on-Don.

Results and Discussions

In accordance with this goal, we have identified several stages of implementation:

At the orientation stage, we identified the levels of perception of speech characteristics of children by parents, and also determined the preferred forms of communication with experts. We defined the level of speech development.

At the organizational stage active activities were implemented in the formation of interaction between the teacher and the parent. In the test they identified the dynamics in the speech development of children and described the results of active forms of interaction between the teacher and parents.

The experiment involved 28 children with general speech disorder attending a correctional kindergarten and 28 parents of these children. The diagnostic study took place in 2 stages: at the first stage we conducted a survey of parents, at the second stage we scrutinized the study of the speech development of children of the experimental group.

Diagnostic tools were developed to study the selected criteria: - parents studied the perception of the peculiarities of speech development of children by a questionnaire designed by us, which included such questions as: What difficulties do you notice in the child's speech? Did you take any steps to correct these difficulties (searching for specialists, consulting with doctors, browsing the Internet, etc.)

When analyzing the answers of parents, we evaluated the understanding of the problems of the child according to the criteria:

- understands the problem of the child, clearly articulates;
- understands that the child has a problem, but formulates it superficially;
- does not understand what the problem is with the child.

The remaining questions revealed a desire to be informed about the speech disorders of their child, the preferred and accessible forms of interaction between teachers and parents, and more. When analyzing the answers to question 9, the following criteria were noted:

- the desire to receive information from a specialist about the speech violations of your child;
- lack of desire to receive information from a specialist about speech violations of your child.

When analyzing the answers to question 10, we evaluated the understanding of problems in raising a child according to the criteria:

- recognition of the difficulties of education;
- not recognition of the difficulties of education.

When analyzing the answers to question 11, we evaluated the preferred forms of work with a specialist according to the following criteria:

- the most preferred forms of communication;
- the least preferred form of communication.

At the second stage, we diagnosed the speech development of children according to the generally accepted speech therapy method (Volkova, 2004).

Thus, we have thought over the content of the research on the issue of interaction with parents in the ONR correction system in younger preschoolers. The content of the work consisted of two stages.

At the first stage, we obtained the following results. When analyzing the questionnaires, we collected data on the family of each child. In the experimental group, more than half of the children were from complete families (86%), more than half of the parents had a high social status (70%), in more than 40% of families, and one of the parents had a higher education. Thus, in general, parents of our pupils are socially prosperous. In studying the difficulties encountered by parents in the course of their upbringing, they revealed a superficial perception of the speech problems of their child. Since the difficulties in the speech of children are not only in the incorrect reproduction of speech, but also in the misunderstanding of the speech of others, the inability to formulate their thoughts, ask questions, etc.

The parents' assessment of their child's speech at the orientation stage of the experiment is presented in Diagram 1.

Diagram 1. The parents' assessment of a child's speech at the orientation stage of the experiment

The next question of the questionnaire is “Would you like to receive information about the features and correction of your child’s speech disorders?” Parents showed a general interest in receiving information (60%), although there were those who thought that the child should be trained by specialists (10%) or one can independently find the necessary information (30%).

The next question “What difficulties in upbringing do you have?” caused numerous heated discussion among parents. All parents, as it turned out, have difficulty in rearing their kids. They encountered such adversity in upbringing as disobedience of the child - 35% of families; lack of support from other family members - 15%; lack of pedagogical knowledge - 20% of families; the child is restless, inattentive - 10%. Thus, 80% of parents noted some problems of upbringing, but there were also parents (20%) who believed that they had no problems in raising a child. This group of parents did not consider it necessary to talk to a speech therapist about their difficulties in communicating with their child.

So, the most preferred types of joint activities of parents and a speech therapist of a preschool, which were identified during the study, are: joint celebration of children’s holidays, activities with children and practical exercises in the form of training, discussions, round tables, seminars; open parental activities (see diagram 2).

Diagram 2. Results of answers to the question: “What forms of interaction with a speech therapist are most appealing to you?”

We also note the least preferred forms of joint activities, such as participation in the work of the parent club, a poster design, joint competitions, and expert consultations.

In order to provide an analysis of the results and stimulate further action to include families in the correction process, a parent meeting was held on the topic “Diagnostic Results. Prospects” parents got acquainted with the results of the survey and, together with the speech therapist, came to the conclusion:

parents need to actively participate in the correction process, strive to get as much information about the features of the disorder and ways of correcting their child's OHP, the involvement of parents in the correction process directly affects the results of children.

At the second stage of the orientation experiment, we diagnosed the speech development of children and revealed the following outcome: 80% of children had a low level of speech development, since they only had phrasal speech, lack of a phonetic-phonemic side, gross lexical and grammatical errors. The remaining children (20%) had an average level of speech development, since their speech was more scarce, in everyday situations children used complex sentences, although the vocabulary was not sophisticated, numerous grammatical errors were observed.

Formative stage

Our in-depth work allowed us to develop an expansive range of programs aimed at the active and effective interaction of speech therapists and parents during the correction process. A long-term plan of interaction with parents was drawn up, the forms of communication that we used during remedial work were selected. Parents were aware of the child's defect and how to eliminate it. We encouraged parents to participate in the remedial process through the introduction of the most effective and preferred forms of work with the family of a young preschool child. To solve this task, we used educational, leisure and visual activities with parents.

The cognitive forms of organizing the communication of teachers with the family are intended to familiarize parents with the peculiarities of the age and psychological development of children, with rational techniques of correcting speech disorders, with ways of developing parents' practical skills in teaching children. Be that as it may, the important role belongs to such forms of communication as meetings, group counseling. At the same time, at the request of parents, we organized events in a non-traditional way, namely: round tables, workshops, master classes, pedagogical briefing, oral pedagogical journals, games with correctional content, a correctional library for parents.

The dialogue between the speech therapist and parents was based on the grounds of a dialogue, openness, sincerity in communication, refusal of criticism and respect for an interlocutor.

The components of the health-preserving activity included in the correctional process of the preschool speech therapist were presented to the parents to be used in the family: gymnastics, finger and breathing exercises. This was done by showing a video made by either the teacher or the parents.

Leisure activities are designed to establish informal rapport between a speech therapist and parents, as well as more trusting relationships between parents and children. Free time activities boost a positive emotional ambiance, parents become more open to communication, and in the future it is easier for speech therapists to establish contacts with them and provide pedagogical information. Joint leisure activities include the participation of parents and children in celebrations, exhibitions, games.

Both parents and children took part in sport and outdoor activities, such as "Merry gymnastics", "Grow as a father" and others. By the same token, joint parent-child events allow seeing the positive aspects of the child. After all, the parent participating in all events knows the problems and ways to overcome them, tries to understand the child's feelings, his point of view. Children's self-esteem and self-confidence increase once they experience love and parental support.

Visual aids solve the problem of familiarizing parents with the conditions, content and methods of correcting speech impairment of children in preschool institutions. The repertoire of techniques allows detecting speech pathology, review methods of correction at home.

We constantly informed parents about the various successes of the child in the classroom, the

condition of each child (his problems and difficulties), and the dynamics of the development of children. Sources of information received from parents are: newspaper issue, family calendars. We provided information in the form of various informational leaflets and booklets, posters, organization of pedagogical mini-libraries, using the Internet space. It is unconventional that for drawing and preparing poster information we attracted parents of children, which caused them a special interest, since they were aware of their responsibility for the timely promotion of relevant information.

One of the most relevant forms of work with the family was child-parent activities: meetings — workshops, game projects, the purpose of which was to create conditions for the establishment and development of partnerships and cooperation between a speech therapist, a parent, and a child.

Also, our work included the use of various forms of work on the number of participants. Collaborative work was carried out when parents could be united according to the common problems that arise in connection with severe violations of the child's speech. In the work of a speech therapist MDOU, the collective form of work is commonplace in group meetings. The task of the general meeting was to discuss with parents the general problems of the correction process, which are important for raising the pedagogical culture of all parents regardless of the age of their children. We acquainted parents with the work of the preschool institution, the program of upbringing and education, talked about the need for carrying out serious correctional and educational work with the children. Reported information about the features of the development of children with ONR and possible pedagogical neglect with improper upbringing. Parents were prepared to understand that they have to make a lot of their own efforts for the development of the child. Speech therapists, teachers, the head took part in the general meeting.

We also applied individual forms of work. Individual forms of work are the most productive in establishing the relationship between the speech therapist and the parents. These forms are represented by: conversation; consultations; individual recommendations.

During the formative experiment, we conducted testing and questioning.

Favorite section of not only parents, but also children – home game stores. Necessary and useful was the method – a piggy bank of methodical recommendations, which worked well in organizing homework by parents in compensatory groups.

The next activity is the parents' five minute talk. They are recommended for work, both at the beginning and at the end of the correction process, where parents received the possibility of short-term personal consultation.

Seminars - workshops were held at the request of the parents. Workshops allowed parents to learn new things, get a step closer to a specialist and become a little speech therapist in their work with their child.

We also spent holidays, entertainment, speech therapy, quizzes. We used this form of work as joint projects. Mailbox "Ask a question to a specialist", this form allows us to provide feedback to parents.

They contain useful information that parents could learn by coming for their children while they were going home. At least once in 2 weeks the material on the poster was updated. Drawings, inscriptions, photos are used in a poster.

The control stage

At the control stage of the experiment, the following results were obtained. To the question "What difficulties do you notice in the child's speech?" We obtained the following results, which are reflected in Diagram 3.

Diagram 3. Assessment of difficulties in the child's speech, according to the parents at the control

stage.

The results of the survey indicate that parents have become more attentive to their children. But the increase in options for the child's difficulties shows that parents in the formative stage of the experiment received enough information to know what problems are, what manifestations of speech disorders in children occur. Parents began to differentiate difficulties in the speech of their children.

The following question of the questionnaire "Would you like to receive information about the features and correction of your child's speech disorders?" Parents gave the following answers: 10% of the parents, although they read the literature on their own questions, didn't exclude those sources that the speech therapist offered them; 90% of families were happy to wait for informative messages. Thus, it was shown that parents began to trust a new source of information, that is, a speech therapist, in obtaining information about the development of their child. From the chart data, we see that after the formative stage of the experiment, the parents had more desire to receive information about the violation of their children. Parents have a need to obtain information about the violation and correction from a specialist who works with their child.

The next question: "What difficulties in upbringing do you have?" At the beginning of the experiment caused a heated discussion among parents. But according to the results of the experimental work it turned out that in the same way that all parents experience difficulties in upbringing. Parents face the following difficulties in parenting: the child's disobedience – 40% of families; do not support other family members – 20%; lack of pedagogical knowledge – 25% of families; the child is restless, inattentive – 15%. From the results it is clear that parents have less difficulty in choosing methods of education, they have enough knowledge with which to overcome various difficulties of the nature and defect of the child. It is now necessary to acquire practical skills in applying various methods of education and training. But now there are other problems. Parents want to engage with their children, but not enough for this time.

To the next question: "What forms of work do you find most interesting?" Parents have already formed preferences for different types of interaction. As a result, we obtained the following options, which are reflected in diagram 4.

Diagram 4. Results of answers to the question: "What forms of work are you most interested in?" at the control stage

So, the most preferred types of joint activities of parents with a speech therapist, which were identified during the study, are: joint activities with children and practical training in the form of training, discussion, round table, seminars; jointly holding children's parties, holding open classes for parents. But there were also other activities in which parents would like to participate.

In the second direction, when diagnosing children's speech development, we saw that the positive results of the interaction between the teacher and the parents had a tremendous impact on the success of the children. Thus, there was a group with a high level of speech development (43%), with an average level of speech development (50%), in which children showed more confident answers in all sections, and although there were 2% of children with a low level, their indicators increased inside groups.

Conclusion

Thus, at the orientation step of the experiment, the stages of the diagnostic work were determined. At the first stage, we diagnosed parental problems in the upbringing and identified the desired forms of work with specialists. In the first stage, parents were surveyed using specially designed questions, and each answer was evaluated according to its own criteria. At the second stage, we diagnosed the speech development of children.

Criteria for assessing the responses of parents were identified, features of the responses of parents were defined and presented in the diagrams.

Then a forming experiment with a variety of activities was carried out. The results of the control experiment showed a positive dynamics of the impact of increased interaction with parents on the success of remedial work, the identified activity of parents influenced the effectiveness of remedial work with children. Children have increased the level of speech development. Thus, we see that after the formative stage of the experiment, interaction with parents in the system of correction of speech impairment among younger students contributed to the formation of a more attentive attitude towards their child, a more precise definition of their violations and difficulties, and also contributed to the interest in the correctional process, and not only to its result. And also in the course of such close cooperation, parents began to more understand the mechanisms of disorder in children, which also contributed to the effectiveness of the joint correctional process, where there is a child – a parent – speech therapist type.

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